

science and policy
for a healthy future

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A (Phased) Plan for Action: Lessons Learned and Recommendations

Deliverable Report

D5.13

WP5 - Translation of results into policy

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Short abstract

In the context of HBM4EU, several participatory case studies have been implemented to facilitate the joint interpretation of HBM-results and their translation into policy options, in co-creation between scientists, policy makers and societal stakeholders. In this deliverable we formulate lessons learned from these case studies and conclude with some recommendations for similar activities in the future.

On the one hand we formulate practical lessons learned from the case studies. On the other hand, we also pay attention to the positioning of this work within HBM4EU and the multi-disciplinary collaboration between social scientists and environmental health scientists that took place for the organisation of these cases.

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1 Introduction

With its slogan '*science and policy for a healthy future*', HBM4EU expresses its ambition to promote not only the coordination and harmonisation of human biomonitoring in Europe, but also the use of this type of evidence for policy making. To this end, a science-to-policy pillar has been established as one of the three pillars of the project. This pillar comprises various activities, one of which is the development of participatory case studies to promote the joint interpretation of HBM results and their translation into potential policy options, in co-creation between scientists, policy makers and societal stakeholders (Work Package 5.5).

This activity was led by the University of Antwerp (Department of Social Sciences, research group CRESC), in close collaboration with VITO (HBM4EU co-coordinator and science-to-policy pillar leader) and the European Environment Agency (EEA), and with dedicated partners for the different case study topics. Both the University of Antwerp and VITO had previous experience with a similar approach in Flanders (Belgium), where a 'phased plan for action' is implemented after each cycle of the Flemish Environment and Health Study (FLEHS) (see box 1). Although not fully transposable to the HBM4EU context, this approach served as a source of inspiration.

In the first year of the project (2017), an exploration was carried out into options and good practices for this type of activity, specifically for the HBM4EU context. A generic canvas was developed with general principles and building blocks, titled: "*A (phased) plan for action: how structured multi-actor dialogues on human biomonitoring results can facilitate targeted policy action*" (see [deliverable AD5.1](#)). This generic canvas was deliberately kept broad enough in focus to allow for different activities in the science-policy interface. A 'canvas' indeed refers to a well-grounded basis for elaborating any 'piece of painting'. It was judged that sufficient flexibility was required and that a fixed script for translating scientific results into policy (such as the Flemish approach, see box 1) was not entirely appropriate. Instead, the focus was rather on several underlying principles: such as the need for multi- and transdisciplinary cooperation in the context of complexity, the need for opportunities to interact and for dialogue between scientific-, policy- and societal stakeholders, the creation of mutual ownership, transparency and a well-structured process architecture.

"Researchers being involved in environmental health research and risk assessment often have reasonable suggestions in mind for interventions and risk management and are able to mobilize additional insights for policy translation. Policy makers and stakeholders on the other hand, can add their interpretation from other contexts and perspectives, imagine futures and can set priorities to frame results, envision measures and judge their political feasibility." (Quote from the generic canvas for structured multi-actor dialogues)

In the subsequent years, three participatory case studies were developed: a first focusing on science-policy aspects of phthalates and bisphenols (2018); a second on PFAS (2020-2021); and a third on HBM4EU indicators for PFAS, phthalates and cadmium (2021-2022). While similar in its objective, each case study was approached differently (see chapter 2).

In this deliverable we formulate lessons learned from these case studies and conclude with some recommendations for similar activities in the future, be it in PARC (the successor of HBM4EU) or in other contexts. On the one hand we formulate practical lessons learned from the case studies. On the other hand, we also pay attention to the positioning of this work within HBM4EU and the multi-disciplinary collaboration between social scientists and environmental health scientists that took place for the organisation of these cases.

Box 1: A ‘phased plan for action’ in Flanders (Belgium) – From human biomonitoring to targeted policy action

Since 2001 the Flemish Center of Expertise on Environment and Health conducts HBM studies in Flanders (Belgium), in different age groups of the general population and in hotspot areas. Both classic pollutants and new emerging substances are monitored over time (Schoeters et al., 2016). To facilitate the uptake of research findings by policymakers and other stakeholders, a ‘phased plan for action’ has been developed collaboratively by scientists of the Centre and policy makers (Keune et al., 2009).

The action plan consists of four consecutive phases and implements an ‘analytic–deliberative’ approach by involving experts, policymakers and stakeholders in each phase (in a structured practice cycle). See **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden..**

By offering a structured and collaborative approach, the ‘phased plan for action’ has the ambition to increase transparency, support and partnership for environmental health policy, based on the best available knowledge. Up to now four FLEHS-cycles were conducted, and after each cycle a successful phased plan for action has been implemented.

Figure 1: The Four Phases and Practice Cycle of the ‘Phased Plan for Action

For a more detailed description, see [deliverable AD5.1](#), or Keune et al., 2009; Reynders et al., 2016.

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2 The case studies

Three in-depth **participatory case studies** on specific substance groups were initiated to stimulate the dialogue between scientists of the HBM4EU consortium and representatives from the European Commission, EU agencies, national authorities and (if the study context allowed) societal stakeholders, to discuss how HBM results can support policy making in different policy domains.

Case study topics were decided after consultation within the consortium and on the basis of specific opportunities with regard to: i) new research results, ii) ongoing or planned policy processes and/or iii) the estimated relevance of a dialogue between a diversity of actors. Although specific opportunities were the starting point for the case studies, the objective was always to initiate a broad dialogue about the relevance of HBM evidence for policy making, with attention to a **diversity of relevant perspectives** and a **diversity of policy instruments, policy domains and policy levels**.

Each case study consisted of several iterative steps, which allowed to gradually develop the case, not only in terms of content but also as a learning process for the various partners involved. Timely preparatory meetings with key partners enabled to better align expectations, refine messages, and increase engagement and shared ownership. This kind of explorative meetings turned out to be fruitful.

Case study on phthalates and bisphenols (2018)

A first case study focused on phthalates and bisphenols, two of the HBM4EU priority substance groups. **Arguments to select this topic** included: i) availability of HBM data from the EU project DEMOCOPHES and several national studies, ii) HBM health-based guidance values being developed at that time under HBM4EU, and iii) a recent REACH restriction proposal for four phthalates on the basis of HBM data from DEMOCOPHES (submitted to the European Commission in the course of the case study, decided in 2018 and came into effect in 2020).

Preparatory **desk research** and 16 bilateral **interviews** with representatives from different EU policy domains and societal stakeholders (NGOs, industry) were carried out to get a better view on the current knowledge base and its appraisal, the policy context, societal concerns and relevant stakeholders.

On 8-9 November 2018 a two-day **workshop** (noon-to-noon) was organised in Brussels, to discuss the use of (existing) HBM data for policy making, with a broad diversity of actors present (see figure).

Key messages from interviews and workshop (2018):

- *“While the debate on phthalates and bisphenols has been ongoing for decades and regulatory actions have been taken, important knowledge gaps persist.*
- *In order to address these gaps, HBM4EU has high scientific ambitions in terms of harmonising approaches, implementing consistent quality control and developing new methods to investigate exposure pathways and health impacts. At the same time, HBM4EU partners are eager to work with risk assessors and managers to produce data and develop tools that can advance their work.*
- *Workshop participants concluded that i) good practices should be developed and actively promoted to demonstrate the added value of Human Biomonitoring, ii) HBM4EU should ensure that outputs are aligned with regulatory needs in terms of who needs what knowledge when and iii) joint reflection on research results is needed to attain robust conclusions for communication and policy making.*
- *Looking forward, a clear role should be assigned to Human Biomonitoring in the regulatory process, as a tool for understanding human exposure to chemicals in Europe.”*

Variety of perspectives involved

A detailed report is available in [Deliverable 5.4](#)

Case study on PFAS (2020-2021)

A second case study focused on PFAS. **Arguments to select this topic** included: early availability of new HBM data from HBM4EU ‘aligned studies’ (although still confidential at that stage) and important changes in the policy context for PFAS (including the publication of a new EFSA opinion, the announcement of a broad PFAS action plan by the European Commission, the intention of several EU member states for a broad PFAS restriction and several PFAS crises at the national level). A dialogue about the importance of HBM research and data in such a policy context was judged to be highly relevant and timely by several closely involved parties.

Preparatory **desk research** and several **meetings with experts within the consortium and key policy actors** were set up as part of an intensive preparatory process for an online science-to-policy workshop.

On 28-29 April 2021 an **online workshop** was organised for HBM4EU experts and risk assessors and managers from the EC, EU-agencies and national authorities, to discuss first

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results from HBM4EU on PFAS as well as policy opportunities, in a confidential setting (given the fact that the new data from HBM4EU were not yet publicly available at that time). Given this confidentiality, it was decided not to invite societal stakeholders for the workshop.

- Participants to the workshop were offered up to date information on HBM4EU results and activities, including information on the HBM studies from various countries in Europe that have been aligned to generate EU-wide HBM data.
- Several policy actors were invited to present up to date information on recent policy developments and how the results of HBM4EU could contribute to these efforts. Presentations provided information on the European commission's PFAS strategy, the restriction intention for the PFAS group as a whole and policy initiatives at the national level, with examples from two EU member states. These presentations illustrated the relevance and use of HBM at different policy levels and for multiple uses.
- The workshop clearly demonstrated the importance of an open and in-depth science-to-policy dialogue between HBM4EU experts, risk managers and risk assessors, across various policy domains and policy levels. Several opportunities for the use of HBM4EU results were identified.

A detailed report is available in [Deliverable 5.7](#)

Case study on HBM4EU indicators for PFAS, phthalates and cadmium (2021-2022).

A third case study aimed to initiate a **multi-criteria appraisal** of new HBM results from the HBM4EU 'aligned studies', as visualised in indicator reports. These indicator reports are important new outputs of the HBM4EU project, and with this science-to-policy initiative we wanted to seize the opportunity to highlight these new results among experts, policy makers and societal stakeholders and give them an opportunity to reflect - in an early stage - on their relevance and usefulness, for their respective working domains. The case study focussed on the substance groups for which the reports were available first (i.e. PFAS, phthalates and cadmium).

In order to guide and structure our appraisal exercise **relevant criteria were defined in a first stage**, in the form of a questionnaire. To check the robustness of these criteria and the questionnaire, a consultation was organised within the HBM4EU consortium to evaluate the criteria in terms of relevance, clarity and completeness. The generic questionnaire was adapted accordingly.

In a second stage, questionnaires for the three substance groups were sent to a diversity of experts, policy actors and stakeholders from the respective HBM4EU advisory boards, asking them to appraise the results on their relevance for science, for policy making and for society, according to the criteria.

Since the response rate to this written survey was rather limited, especially on the part of policy actors and societal stakeholders, **we also asked participants of an online science-to-policy workshop to fill out a shortened and anonymous online version of the questionnaire**, after becoming acquainted with the new results on the same groups of substances (+ bisphenols), through presentations by HBM4EU colleagues. The response rate for this additional survey was more satisfactory from the angle of policy actors, which enabled us to better estimate the expected relevance of the new results for policy makers. Societal stakeholders were not invited for the workshop, so the low response rate from this angle was not compensated.

A detailed report will become available in Deliverable 5.10 (expected May/June 2022)

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In addition to these case studies, two additional but related tasks were initiated in the context of WP 5.5:

1. Given the need to consolidate messages on aligned study results internally within the consortium, VITO, DOMG, EEA and UAntwerpen elaborated a workflow for internal steps of consolidation: with the study PI's, the statistical working group (WP10), the chemical group leaders, the Management Board, the Policy Board and Stakeholder Forum and the national hubs ('Strategy for making new HBM4EU results available from the aligned studies' by VITO, DOMG, UAntwerpen, EEA (HBM4EU knowledge hub, 2020-2021)). The guidelines help to anticipate barriers and divergent interpretations of the results in a timely way, before results are released to external parties and the public at large. In the workflow, feedback loops are integrated, contributing to the necessary flexibility. Box 2 elaborates on the stepwise approach for communication of the results stemming from the HBM4EU aligned studies.

Box 2: Strategy for making new HBM4EU results available from the aligned studies

Stepwise approach for communication of EU level results:				
	WHAT	WHO IS INVOLVED	WHEN	WHO IS RESPONSIBLE
1	Quality control <i>Key messages</i> <i>Uncertainties</i> <i>Policy relevance</i>	WP10 substance lead <-> PI's of national studies (+ CGL, WP9, WP14 & Statistics Working Group)	ASAP	The specific partner leading the task that delivers the result
	Dissemination and communication of national results. <i>To the study participants, granting authorities and national/regional government, ethics committee,...</i>	PI's of national studies, NH's, funding authorities,.. ▽ △	ASAP <i>(conform national requirements!)</i>	PI of national studies
2	Consolidation of key messages + Develop communication plan <i>Targeted audience(s)</i> <i>Type of communication product</i> <i>Timeline</i>	WP8 & WP10-leader ¹ & coordinator knowledge hub ▽ △	ASAP	The specific partner leading the task that delivers the result
3	Validation of HBM4EU product <i>(or conflict resolution)</i>	Management Board <i>(via WP-leader & coordinator knowledge hub)</i> ▽	4 weeks before communication day ²	WP lead
4	Prior notification	EU PB – confidentially! ▽	10 working days before communication day	Knowledge hub
	Prior notification	GB, NHCPs – confidentially! ▽		UBA & NH Coördinator
5	[Optional: Announcement]	[SF, other external fora] ▽	Communication day	Maria Uhl & Knowledge hub
6	Communication & dissemination	Public communication and dissemination	Communication day	Knowledge hub

2. At the request of the HBM4EU Advisory Board, we also contributed to the development of an approach to more explicitly and systematically anticipate relevant ongoing policy processes and opportunities for the use of HBM4EU results (see box 3 and [additional deliverable 5.9](#)).

Box 3: Timelines of Opportunity

The ‘timelines of opportunity’ refer to a strategy that has been developed and tested in the context of HBM4EU for **keeping track of specific policy opportunities (e.g. a planned risk assessment or a decision-making process) for which HBM4EU can deliver relevant evidence on time**. The strategy includes a mapping of the ‘policy timeline(s)’ on the one hand, and the ‘project timeline(s)’ on the other hand, in order to make explicit where both timelines are compatible with each other.

In developing this strategy, explicit emphasis was placed on the belief that information from HBM and HBM-related studies can be important for a **broad variety of policy processes**. These include (regulatory) risk assessment and policy evaluation, agenda-setting and prioritisation, awareness raising of the population, or stakeholder initiatives (e.g. by NGOs or voluntary action by companies or sectors). Specific data analysis can also inform targeted policy interventions for specific sectors or vulnerable groups.

Table 2 illustrates different types of output from the HBM4EU project, its policy relevance and key actors that might be interested in results (without the intention to capture all HBM4EU results and type of actors).

TYPES OF PROJECT OUTPUT, POLICY RELEVANCE AND KEY ACTORS INVOLVED (FROM EU PERSPECTIVE)

	TYPES OF OUTPUT	POLICY RELEVANCE	KEY ACTORS
	(New) HBM data , Europe-wide exposure data	Realistic exposure assessment , in context of risk assessment and health impact assessment.	ECHA (RAC), EFSA and other expert committees, risk assessors national authorities, ...
	Socio-demographic- (age, vulnerable groups) and geographic stratification	Input for targeted policy initiatives (both regulatory and non-regulatory). Input for national, regional, social policy, health promotion	ECHA, DG SANTE, DG EMPL, EU OSHA, National/regional/local Authorities, civil society and sector organisations, ...
	HBM Guidance Values	Prioritisation, health surveillance	Risk assessors, EC (DG ENV, DG SANTE), EP, Council of Ministers, Member States, civil society, ...
	Time trends	Evaluation, prioritisation, health surveillance	EC (DG ENV), EP, Council of Ministers, Member States, civil society, ...
	Exposure pathways analysis; determinants analysis	Input for sectoral policies, exposure prevention (health promotion)	EFSA, DG ENV (product standards), EMA, industry and sector associations, civil society, ...
	Effect monitoring, exposure-effect associations	Input for hazard assessment , in context of RA, HIA, classification, SVHC listing, ...	ECHA (RAC), EFSA and other expert committees, risk assessors national authorities, ...
	Monitoring of new emerging chemicals , non-targeted screening	Early warning	EC, EP, Council of Ministers, Member States, DG ENV, DG EMPL, EU OSHA, ...

... This table illustrates the diversity of HBM4EU's output, its respective policy relevance and a selection of key actors that might be interested in results. This table does not necessarily provide a complete overview ...

Table 2: Table from Research Brief on ‘Timelines of Opportunity - How HBM4EU can support chemicals management policy needs’

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3 Lessons learned

3.1 Lessons learned from the case studies

3.1.1 Success factors

We look back satisfied with the three case studies. For the first two cases, a good representation of the intended target groups was achieved and a thoroughly-prepared and in each case a successful two-day workshop was organised. Evaluation surveys after the workshops also showed that most participants were satisfied with the way in which the workshops were organised. Most appreciation went to the opportunities that were offered to provide input and to enter into discussion. A big majority of participants indicated that they will use what they have learned in their respective organisations and networks.

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. summarises some of the statements we received through the evaluation forms, and more detailed results of the workshop-evaluations are presented in the respective reports ([deliverable 5.4](#) and [deliverable 5.7](#)).

Figure 2: Statements from workshop participants (evaluation PFAS workshop 28-29 April 2021)

The third case was also satisfactory, but had to deal with obstacles during its implementation. The science-policy initiative had to be redefined more than once during 2021 due to delays in the processing of the study results, mainly due to covid related delays in the labs. This was also the case for the second case study, but as the project was coming close to its end, there was little room to adjust the plans in time. As a result, it was necessary to work with confidential results (as was also the case for the second case), which limits the scope and impact of the exercise. A second important disadvantage was that the appetite for a written survey was clearly less present, compared to the interest we experienced in the first two cases with (in both cases) a lively workshop at the end. In particular, the extensive written survey was barely answered by policy actors and stakeholders. From a few respondents, we also received the answer that the questions went beyond their mandate, so they decided not to send in an answer. The shorter and completely

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anonymous version of the questionnaire in the margins of the 30-31 March 2022 science-to-policy workshop had a better response rate. The fact that the online survey took little time from the respondents, in combination with the anonymity of the responses, might be important factors explaining this higher response rate. We are convinced that civil servants as well as researchers are crucial partners in the matchmaking of science and policy perspectives. However, this experience confirms the more comfortable setting that informal meetings offer for this kind of interaction. The major advantage of the written survey format was that we obtained similar substantive input for different substance groups (PFAS, bisphenols, phthalates/DINCH, and cadmium).

Factors that we believe have contributed to the successful case studies include:

- a) Sufficient space for dialogue

In the agendas for the workshops, about 50% of the time was reserved for discussion. Both for (factual) questions after the presentations, as well as for discussion on specific topics. Relevant topics for discussion were identified in advance through preparatory discussions with key actors.

- b) A well-balanced group of participants

The aim was always to involve a sufficiently diverse group of participants with relevant perspectives. For each of the most important perspectives, we at least invited one representative, while at the same time trying not to make the group too large which is important to enable sufficient interaction during the discussions. Good stakeholder mapping and personal, targeted and timely contact with potential participants proved to be crucial in achieving this goal. This requires a considerable investment of time on top of the substantive preparation of the content and practicalities of the workshop.

- c) The willingness of most invited actors to participate in a dialogue on the (potential) role and added value of HBM in EU- and national policy making

Although some kind of legal mandate or institutionalised framework for HBM in Europe is currently still missing, there seems to be a clear and growing interest in HBM from a policy and societal perspective. Perhaps (in part) because it clearly highlights several 'new' challenges in chemical management practices and advocates a more integral approach. HBM research makes very visible that we are exposed to a cocktail of (low levels of) chemical substances and that exposure-effect associations are found also below previously assumed 'safe levels'. HBM provides a measure for integral exposure, from various sources and exposure routes, which puts pressure on the fragmentation of the various policy domains. HBM also responds to the increased awareness of the public on topics such as endocrine disruption and the effects (for instance of PFAS) on the immune system.

- d) Dedication of project partners

Dedication of project partners is important to support the case studies substantively, e.g. by presenting research results and background knowledge and participating in the discussions. In particular the science-to-policy pillar leader (VITO) and chemical group leaders for the respective substance groups played an important role in identifying key outcomes and activities of the project, opportunities for dialogue and in motivating other project partners to get involved.

- e) Intensive and iterative preparation of the workshops

The preparation of the workshops was intensive and iterative, including actor mapping and contact, frequent contact about the workshop agenda and presentations. This allowed to gradually develop

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the case, not only in terms of content but also as a learning process for the various partners involved. Timely preparatory meetings with key partners enabled to better align expectations, refine messages, and increase engagement and shared ownership.

Table 1: Ingredients for a well-prepared workshop:

<p>Preparation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defining the workshop's goals and outcome Defining the speaker's list, cooperating actors, moderators and note takers Defining the workshop's agenda Preparing information package for participants Preparing the workshop's script: who - does what - when <p>Set-up</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sending invitations Monitoring the (balance) of categories of participants Set up room / virtual room Break-out groups Catering <p>Opening</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explaining the procedure, expected outcome(s), processing the input received Explaining programme and schedule Explaining rules of anonymity and representation Explaining rules with regard to recording and data treatment Launching the questions <p>Closing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main messages and conclusions Discussing the conclusions Explaining what to expect next, prospects and outreach Optional: inviting attendees to fill out evaluation form <p>Reporting-back</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Summarising the responses or summary of conclusions Invitation to feed-back on the draft report Analysis and evaluation Release of the report

f) Active communication

Networking for such initiatives only works well if sufficient attention is paid to a timely and responsive manner of communication and keeping everyone well informed.

g) A safe environment to speak

During the workshops, it was always explicitly emphasised that participants could speak in their own name, from their own professional experience, but not as a (mandated) spokesperson for their organisation. Recordings were made for reporting purposes only and were not made available afterwards. Specific quotes were only included in the reporting if this provided added value and

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after approval of the participants involved. This context allowed participants to speak freely, resulting in lively discussions.

h) Empathy for boundary work

Science-policy translation is not to be understood as a clearly delineated *linear* process (Sabatier, 2007). It is important to offer opportunities for matchmaking between the different perspectives, to choose for selective focusses and to actively take into account the specific characteristics of the worlds of research, risk assessment, and regulation/policy making. The discussions demonstrate that researchers are eager to reflect upon policy recommendations or at least risk reducing options and that policy representatives are capable to reflect upon research outcomes and the quality of the knowledge base for further action. During the workshops, common interpretations are made and mutually verified. This does not mean that both parties interfere or step in each other's roles or that they would lose their neutrality or professionalism. It is precisely these interactions that 'construct' the divisions between science and policy (Gieryn, 1999) and that clarify the distinct roles instead of static criteria to distinguish science from non-science in an absolute sense. We also refer to the point below on the challenges with regard to the formulation of policy questions.

Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic?

The COVID-restrictions first seemed to restrict our interactive research activities as it was impossible to organise on location workshops, but in the end, we discovered many new advantages of gathering and meeting online. The online dialogues altered the interaction format but enriched it as well:

- There were less concerns on the ideal location for the workshops and on travel distance and peripheral drop-out; more participants were able to join as no travel costs were implied;
- This also goes for financially solid institutions because some participants are not allowed to be remunerated for travels and stays; there was a more equal treatment of official bodies (not accepting remuneration for travels) and NGOs;
- The online application's facilities to virtually raise hands offered a fair turn for speaking and safeguarded the virtual proximity;
- Chat facilities launched an additional exchange of information and discussions, as well during as after the sessions for the reporting;
- Different formats for meeting in break-out groups.

Major disadvantages of online interactive sessions are:

- The lack of opportunity for informal networking and debriefing;
- The needed digital literacy might entail new forms of social exclusion;
- The length of the workshop is to be kept as short as possible to prevent digital fatigue.

3.1.2 Challenges

Despite the success of the case studies and satisfaction among most of the actors involved, we also encountered several challenges along the way.

a) Late availability of new research results

The participatory case studies in WP5.5, and by extension all activities in WP5, were initially aimed at translating (new) scientific results of HBM4EU into policy action, or at least facilitating the uptake of the findings by policy makers and other stakeholders. In that respect, the timely availability of

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new results was an important factor for these activities. Gradually, however, it became clear that there was still too much preparatory and 'institutional' work needed to deliver these new data (and derived research results). Collecting, merging and comparing existing HBM databases in the EU turned out to be quite a challenge, and also for the co-financed HBM4EU aligned studies, a lot of 'infrastructure' had to be developed first, e.g. for quality control, Standard Operating Procedures, communication agreements, and so on. On top, there was also the delay caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Because of that, the first case study focused on already existing and known data (from the DEMOCOPHES study).

But where this could still be justified for a first case study, we wanted to wait for new results before starting a second case study. This has repeatedly led to the postponement of case 2 and case 3, and ultimately the need to organise the last two cases in a confidential setting (since the new results were eventually there, but not yet publicly available). Although there are important scientific arguments for this delayed availability of data and results (e.g. with regard to scientific quality and peer review), this clearly hindered the organisations of all kinds of risk governance activities that could have been set-up in the context of HBM4EU (see also below).

Nevertheless, sufficient opportunities for interaction were found within the direct bodies of HBM4EU itself, in some cases extended to non-directly involved actors from the DGs, agencies and involved countries. The consultation of these bodies offered a welcome alternative and the search for redefinition of the cases in the evolving research context was always well supported by our WP- and science-policy pillar leader, Greet Schoeters. The late availability of new and public research results was mainly at the expense of involvement of societal stakeholder groups and public communication of the conclusions of the case studies. This kind of consultations would have brought us further with the interpretations of external parties that are strongly involved in the domain of risk regulation and management and the bottom up initiatives of market parties, of consumer and environmental groups.

b) A dominant focus on regulation (at EU level)

Although we tried to focus attention on a diversity of policy instruments in the different case studies, we always experienced a dominant focus on regulation at the EU level, while other types of policy instruments may have a greater, or at least a significant additional impact on reducing environmental health risks. Because many of these other types of policy instruments are still the responsibility of national or local governments, various attempts have been made to bring that national perspective 'to the table', e.g. by inviting sufficient representation from national (and regional) governments, putting 'testimonials' about national cases on the agenda, or presenting an overview with examples of various policy instruments (see illustration), but the attention for regulation has always been dominant. In terms of chemical policy at the EU level, this is perhaps where the main interest lies, also for the national representatives. Of course, people and organisations involved in other types of policy areas can always be specifically searched for, but an overarching discussion about various types of policy instruments, and which of those instruments are the most legitimate or effective for managing certain environmental health risks, proved difficult to achieve.

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Figure 3: Mapping of relevant policy instruments for the phthalates and bisphenol case (2018) (deliverable 5.4)

c) EU level versus the national- and local level?

Linked to the previous point: we found it often difficult to pay sufficient attention to the various added values that a (European) HBM programme also has for the national and local level. And this despite the fact that the various national governments have contributed a significant part of the budget for HBM4EU in the form of co-financing. In our case studies we have always tried to give explicit attention to the national component, as has also happened in other project meetings and conferences. Nevertheless, it has remained a largely underexposed aspect, about which we also noticed some dissatisfaction among some other partners in the project.

d) Topical expertise versus 'helicopter perspective'

When organisations were invited to participate in the case studies, most organisations were often inclined to delegate their content experts on the specific substance groups. However, for the type of dialogue we wanted to initiate, it was also desirable for the participants to be able to reflect from a broader, 'helicopter' perspective.

For example, in order to be able to participate in a discussion about which type of policy instrument is most suitable as a policy response to certain identified environmental health risks, you often have to be able to look outside the framework of your own field of work, or the specific interest that your organisation promotes. On the one hand, this may have to do with prioritising the public interest over the interests of one's own organisation. On the other hand, it is also about broader knowledge about the functioning and possibilities, or limitations of other actors, and policy making in general. This once again underlines the importance of a good preparatory process in which sufficient investments are made in the search for suitable candidates to participate in the case studies.

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3.2 Lessons learned on the role of this work within HBM4EU

While the previous lessons are closely related to the three case studies, in this section we briefly reflect on the role of these activities within HBM4EU. As a small team of three social scientists, we were invited to participate in the project to support the science-to-policy interface, based on the experiences we had with similar projects in Flanders. A very interesting, but challenging experience.

a) Risk governance and boundary work

From the perspective of the risk governance cycle (see Figure 4), HBM4EU remained primarily a scientific research project. With a lot of attention for data collection and (policy-oriented) research questions. In Figure 4, HBM4EU researchers will also recognise terms such as risk assessment, early warning and monitoring, but these also remain closely linked to the scientific practice.

There is of course nothing wrong with that, especially for a project that is for a large part financed by the EU's Directorate General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD). But as Figure 4 shows, many other relevant activities take place in the interface between science and policy, which play an important role in the 'translation' of knowledge into policy action. With our case studies in HBM4EU, some further steps were taken in the direction of those other activities, such as concern assessment, risk evaluation and option identification, but not to the extent that we can say that it was a structural way of working within the project. The small proportion of social- and policy scientists, as well as the absence of e.g. economic sciences within the project, is an obvious reflection of that. Except for our small team of three social scientists, we did not come across any other similar profiles, in a very large group of scientists.

It must also be said that this type of activity requires for many of those involved to step outside of their own comfort zone, or vice versa to allow others to think along about what is perceived as their own field of work. Indeed, we regularly found that many scientists, as well as government agencies (both at EU and national level) are very careful to go beyond their own expertise or mandate. Or vice versa, that scientists find it difficult to accept when policy actors join in the assessment of health concerns or the quality of the knowledge base, as well as policy actors finding it difficult to accept when scientists tell what policy makers should do. During the final conference (Brussels 27-28 April 2022), the science-policy pillar coordinator also testified to a historic evolution in the project: initially, the group of researchers from the different countries was very hesitant to interact with policy authorities. Yet this interaction (or 'matchmaking') is exactly what is needed in the interface between science and policy. And as already mentioned in section 3.1.1. (on 'empathy for boundary work') our case studies show that such interaction is possible and can lead to a kind of shared interpretation, while still respecting each other's role and identity. At the same time, we found that such an interaction was easier to realise in an informal (and if necessary confidential) workshop setting. In the written survey in case 3, there was clearly more reluctance to express oneself about questions or criteria that did not belong to one's own discipline or field of work.

Figure 4: The risk governance framework (International Risk Governance Council, 2017)

Another example of the ‘boundary work’ that took place within the project, are the policy questions that were formulated at the very start of HBM4EU (in WP 2), for each of the priority substance groups. From the perspective of a social scientist, most of these questions do not reflect the typical nature of a policy question. They were for a large part phrased as knowledge and research needs, instead of e.g. questions on effectiveness and efficiency in risk management and chemicals policy, or questions on trade-offs, proportionality and consistency in decision-making, for which evaluation criteria should be made explicit. A policy question usually involves not only an assessment of knowledge or the burden of proof, but also a balancing of various concerns and a value judgement.

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A research question on the other hand, frames the addressed societal and policy demands into knowledge needs and manageable research terms. In addition, scientific uncertainty often has to be considered and how to deal with it in a policy and societal context.

The distinct roles should always be respected but one cannot deny the grey zones between research activities and policy making in which the (safe and exploratory) interaction precisely learns us to detect and appreciate these differences. This brings us again to the section on empathy for boundary work. It would be good that PARC takes position with regard to the strategies that e.g. Aven & Renn (2018) consider as favorable for risk management related science-policy issues. Even a strict focus on the knowledge/evidence base for chemical substances raises questions on the criteria to be used for risk evaluation and thus will partly be societal in nature.

b) Social sciences specialisation

Although we were happy to join the research activities of such an important project, it would definitely have been more comfortable to have more teams from the social sciences and humanities on board, for the exchange of findings and the international networking with other teams that specialise in the different aspects of risk governance. Risk governance is not only about risk communication and sociology, but also about political processes, policy evaluation and public policy sciences.

The 3 researchers reflected these different backgrounds, which was welcome to deal with the diversity of aspects within the HBM4EU-research work: understanding the societal aspects of risk assessment practices and risk governance; insight in divergent risk perception and the amplification of risk perception, stakeholder mapping, the design of questionnaires and interactive workshops, guidance of science-policy dialogues as intensive processes, identifying different types of policy instruments, providing criteria for policy evaluation, fulfilling ethics requirements for the social sciences and humanities (see also next section). Throughout these research activities, we tried to act as change agents, trying to raise awareness on the societal, policy and political aspects, but also as flies on the wall, observing the perspectives and practices of the biomedical researchers, toxicologists etc.

For future initiatives we would recommend to first clearly define a delineated set of autonomous social scientific research questions. Our roles in HBM4EU now happened to evolve strongly as goal-seeking objectives and process related tasks, which is a challenging research position in a strictly arranged administrative project environment. Next to that substantive role, opportunity should be kept open for the follow up of the different interesting bodies and work packages in the research consortium and to selectively attend its meetings.

c) Ethics requirements

The need for social scientists in international human biomonitoring activities will also increase given ethics requirements with regard to the organisation of e.g. focus groups, questionnaires and workshops on societal and policy aspects of research in the domain of risk governance. These requirements are often considered as additional work and bureaucracy but they gain field for legitimising social scientific findings (a condition for instance for publishing results in peer reviewed journals) and not only for the protection of the researcher and his or her respondents. The HBM4EU consortium had the chance to fall back on the ethics panels of the universities for these activities (EAA and UAntwerpen for instance).

Most of the public health institutes do not have separate facilities for the processing of ethics requirements in the domain of social sciences and humanities. Thanks to the installation of a

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HBM4EU ethics panel (WP1) we were able to suggest pragmatic ethics guidelines for the future. It is recommended to arrange the expectations with regard to questionnaires, workshops, surveys addressed at governmental representatives, stakeholders and citizens in advance, going beyond what is required in the domain of the biomedical research activities. Revealing risk perceptions or concern assessments can not only “identify and explain public concerns“ and “enhance understanding of controversies about risk evaluation“ but also “can provide criteria for evaluating risk management performance and organisational structures for monitoring and controlling risks” (Aven & Renn: 2018).

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4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the importance of creating sufficient opportunities for interaction between scientists, policymakers and societal stakeholders in a project such as HBM4EU is beyond dispute. Concrete cases about specific (new) research results are a good occasion for that. It triggers relevant actors to participate in the dialogue and offers a good topic for a constructive conversation that can partly transcend the continuous repetition of controversial or well-known discussions. We are confident that the case studies conducted in WP5.5, as briefly described in this deliverable, demonstrate this. This also offers great opportunities for PARC, the successor to HBM4EU, because many new results will emerge from HBM4EU in the past and coming months.

In section 3.1 we have listed some points that we believe can contribute to a successful dialogue. This concerns, among other things, the importance of an extensive and iterative preparatory process, the commitment of key actors within the project who can both mobilise the network and have a good substantive overview of what is going on in the project (such as dedicated 'Chemical Group Leaders'), good stakeholder mapping and composition of a well-balanced and active group of participants, and sufficient space for discussion (e.g. in the workshop agendas and preparatory meetings). At the same time, we also found that an interactive, informal, and sometimes confidential setting can yield more results than a written survey, with regard to which many actors appear to have reservations.

While HBM4EU has been able to innovate the science-to-policy interface in the field of chemicals management and environmental health, there will still be a lot of work in the future to embed risk governance activities more structurally, e.g. in PARC. In this regard it seems recommended to develop a broader network in the social sciences and humanities for environmental health. Not only for process-related activities, but also for more autonomous research activities.

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